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Policy Brief:
**“Powering Equality:
An Intersectional Approach
to Gender-Sensitive Careers
in the Energy Sector and
Energy Transformation”**

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Introduction

The green and digital transitions are reshaping Europe's energy landscape, creating unprecedented demand for new skills, interdisciplinary expertise, and diverse talent. At the same time, the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the ERA Policy Agenda underline the obligation to promote equality, non-discrimination, and inclusive labour markets across all sectors. Despite these commitments, the energy sector continues to be shaped by persistent gender inequalities, structural biases, and cultural norms that limit women's participation and advancement. Women's opportunities, constraints, and pathways into the energy sector are shaped by the intersection of multiple identities – including socio-economic background, geography, ethnicity, disability, disciplinary identity (STEM vs. SSH), and family status. Achieving a just energy transformation requires more than increasing the number of women in classrooms or workplaces. It demands deep structural change across educational institutions, labour markets, leadership structures and societal norms.

This policy brief applies an intersectional lens to evidence from focus group interviews and national workshops conducted within the gEneSys project with students, academics, industry professionals, and public officials across Germany, Italy, Poland, and the UK¹. It synthesises barriers, enablers and structural conditions needed to ensure inclusive participation in the emerging energy landscape. It provides evidence-based recommendations to support EU institutions, Member States, higher education institutions, and industry stakeholders in advancing intersectional and gender-sensitive policies in the energy domain.

¹ An extended report from the focus group interviews and workshops can be found here: [D.3.3 - Analyses of and Recommendations for Training Programmes on Gender-Sensitive Energy Transition](#)

Main Results From Interviews and Workshops

Structural and Cultural Barriers in Education and Skills Development

- **Early socialisation shapes career aspirations long before university.** Participants described how girls are taught (explicitly or subtly) to avoid technical fields, discouraged from risk-taking, and often praised for compliance rather than ambition.
- **Stereotypes** – sometimes disguised as “protective” attitudes – continue to influence family choices, teacher expectations, and employer behaviour.
- Across energy-related higher education, gender is largely absent as a topic of study or a structural priority. Students frequently described their programmes as “**gender-neutral or gender-blind**”, noting the lack of explicit integration of gender analysis in curricula or classroom discussions. Gender content, when present, was occasionally introduced by individual lecturers as part of broader themes such as energy justice but was not institutionalised within teaching structures. This absence contributes to low awareness among students of gendered dynamics in the energy labour market.

Barriers to Career Entry and Progression

- **Discipline:** Social science profiles – often including many women – are undervalued despite their relevance for system transition and citizen engagement.
- **Cultural norms**, including the perception of energy-related professions as male

domain and expectations in some cultural groups that undermine women’s authority in technical fields.

- **Information gap on career opportunities in energy-sector.**
- **Territorial disparities** (e.g., between metropolitan and peripheral regions) influence access to internships, training, and job opportunities.
- **Workplace safety and stereotypes:** Women face biased assumptions about physical ability, risk tolerance, or suitability for fieldwork, particularly in nuclear or conventional energy settings.
- **Maternity and care responsibilities** can stall progression when flexibility or institutional supports are lacking.
- **Meritocracy rhetoric** in some national contexts obscures structural inequalities, framing gender-targeted measures as illegitimate despite evidence of implicit bias in recruitment and assessment.
- **Male-dominated professional networks** and informal decision-making channels impede women’s advancement and visibility
- Lack of gender parity reduces the likelihood of cultural change; evidence indicates that a **critical mass of at least 30% women** is necessary to shift norms.

For women facing compounded marginalisation (e.g., ethnic minority women, women with disabilities, first-generation graduates), these barriers are intensified.

Enablers of Inclusion and Participation

Across countries, key enablers include:

- **Women in leadership positions** – both in academia and industry – serve as powerful **role models** and help legitimize women's presence in male-dominated areas.
- **Interdisciplinary programmes** that bridge STEM and SSH, making the field more accessible to a wider range of students.
- **Practical experience** (internships, labs, international placements) which is particularly critical for students lacking professional networks.
- **Supportive supervisors, partners/ family members, or teachers** who actively counter stereotypes.
- **Transparent hiring and promotion systems**, which reduce discretionary bias.
- **Organisational policies** addressing gender, care responsibilities, generation, and diversity, not merely tokenistic quotas.

Policy Recommendations

Recommendations for EU Institutions

- Mainstream intersectional gender analysis across **energy, skills, cohesion, and digitalisation policies** (e.g., Green Deal, REPowerEU, European Skills Agenda).
- Promote disaggregated data collection (gender, age, disability, socio-economic background, migration background, geography) in EU-funded projects and national monitoring.
- Develop EU-wide guidance for **gender-responsive and inclusive green skills strategies**.
- Strengthen support for women from disadvantaged regions through targeted scholarships, mobility schemes, and mentoring initiatives.
- Support regional partnerships linking education providers, companies, and public authorities to reduce territorial inequalities.
- Encourage companies to adopt **transparent, inclusive recruitment and promotion frameworks, including reporting on gender pay gap and promotion rates**.
- Demonstrate visible, sustained **national-level commitment to initiatives promoting gender equality** in the energy system to raise the awareness and build the broad societal support for meaningful change.

Recommendations for Member States

- Integrate intersectional gender equality objectives into **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)** and **national skills strategies**.
- Implement **national-level grants, incubators, and entrepreneurship programmes** to support women-led start-ups and innovation projects in energy sector.

- Integrate **gender equality into primary and secondary education curricula**, challenging stereotypes about technical careers and providing early exposure to energy sector.

Recommendations for Higher Education Institutions

- Embed **gender equality and intersectionality across STEM and energy-related programmes**, including through compulsory modules and case studies.
- Increase **female representation** in senior academic and administrative positions.
- Establish new **interdisciplinary programmes and fields** (e.g., Systems Transition Engineering) that integrate engineering, social sciences, and policy studies, where gender, intersectionality, and sustainability are embedded from inception.
- Provide **flexible learning pathways** for students balancing study, work, or caregiving responsibilities.
- Support **women's networks** to exchange knowledge and advocacy.

Recommendations for Companies and Industry Actors

- Implement evidence-based dynamic **equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) strategies aligned with EU standards and intersectional principles**, including

targets, timelines, monitoring and accountability mechanisms.

- Ensure **transparent career progression, objective evaluation criteria, and gender-balanced selection panels**.
- Provide **flexible working conditions and comprehensive support for employees with caring responsibilities** (parental leave, hybrid work, adjusted working hours, return-to-work programmes following long-term leaves).
- Develop **inclusive professional networks and mentoring schemes** for underrepresented groups.
- Challenge **workplace stereotypes** about women's capability for technical and field-based roles through **targeted awareness campaign and evidence-based job design**.

Recommendations for Civil Society and Local Authorities

- Promote **energy literacy initiatives** targeting women and marginalised communities.
- Strengthen **participatory governance in local renewable energy projects**.
- Facilitate **partnerships between NGOs, schools, and municipalities** to support inclusive career awareness.

Conclusions

Achieving gender equality in the energy sector requires coordinated actions across all levels – from the EU policy frameworks to national strategies, industry, educational institutions and civil society practices. Without intentional interventions, structural and cultural barriers will continue to limit women’s participation in this sector. Success

depends on three pillars: systemic change through gender-sensitive policies and data collection, educational transformation and inclusive workplace cultures. With the energy transition accelerating, embedding gender equality as a core principle is not only a matter of justice but also innovation.

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Policy Brief: “Gender Sensitive Education For Energy”

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Transformative Education For Sustainable Transition

As the energy sector undergoes rapid transformation

– driven by the green transition, digitalization, and increasing societal demands for sustainability – education emerges as a decisive arena shaping the future of citizens, communities, as well as different areas such as labour market. The proper energy education creates new opportunities for governments, institutions, and local actors to build more inclusive, informed, and resilient societies.

First, inclusiveness in energy education is no longer optional. Ensuring equal access to knowledge about energy – from everyday consumption to participation in the energy transition – helps prevent both social and energy-related exclusion. It also forms the foundation of a just transition that leaves no individual or community behind.

Second, developing innovative knowledge for social change serves as a catalyst for new models of thinking and action. Interdisciplinary learning that integrates science, technology, and social understanding fosters creativity, pro-environmental attitudes, and the competencies essential for a low-carbon economy.

Third, the growing importance of energy citizenship, informed energy consumption, and education for careers in the energy sector highlights the need to empower learners. Education enables people to shift from being passive energy users to active participants who understand and engage with the tools of the transition – from energy efficiency to local energy production. At the same time, it opens pathways towards

careers in renewable energy, emerging technologies, and energy management, addressing global workforce needs.

An equally critical dimension of the energy – education nexus is gender equality. Women and girls remain underrepresented in STEM fields, particularly in energy-related studies and professions, despite their crucial role in driving social and technological innovation. Integrating gender-sensitive approaches into curricula, leadership programmes, and career guidance can help dismantle barriers that limit participation and advancement. By promoting female role models, ensuring inclusive learning environments, and addressing gender stereotypes embedded in both education and the energy sector, policymakers can unlock the full potential of diverse talent. Strengthening gender equality not only contributes to a more equitable society but also expands the workforce needed for an effective, innovative, and socially responsive energy transition.

These pillars outline the essential directions for ensuring that education systems become a driving force behind a just, sustainable, and innovative energy transition.

10 Policy Recommendations

1. Make energy a focal point across the entire education pathway

Energy should be treated as a core subject from early childhood through adult learning. Early exposure builds foundational understanding, fosters energy competencies and counters gender stereotypes, and helps establish energy as a universal competency rather than a specialist niche. This integration should be age-appropriate and interdisciplinary: primary students exploring energy through hands-on experiments and connecting it to daily life; secondary students analysing energy systems, policy, and justice issues through project-based learning; higher education developing specialized expertise while making energy literacy accessible across all disciplines. Implementation requires redesigning curricula to embed energy across subjects (not as additional content), comprehensive teacher training, and partnerships between educational institutions, energy providers, and communities.

2. Start early to shape energy literacy and inclusive attitudes

Primary and lower-secondary education must introduce energy as part of everyday life, present diverse role models, and challenge gendered assumptions about technology and careers. Early interventions prevent the reproduction of male-dominated energy identities.

3. Build comprehensive energy skills for all learners

Education must support skills for:

- **Energy citizenship** (rights, justice, participation).
- **Energy consumption** (informed decision-making, digital skills, energy competencies).
- **Energy career** (STEM + SSH integration, systems thinking, green skills, leadership). A modern energy transition requires competencies that go far beyond technical knowledge.

4. Treat energy as an interdisciplinary topic connected to real-life practices

Energy should no longer be viewed exclusively as a technical subject. Curricula should link energy to sustainability, social practices, ethics, care work, digitalisation, and community life. Showing the societal relevance of energy boosts engagement and widens participation.

5. Use inclusive language to shape cultural change

Gender-inclusive, gender-sensitive language and visual representation should be standard in all educational and professional materials. Avoid masculine-coded framings and train educators in gender-sensitive communication to counter the belief that energy is “too technical” or male”.

6. Embed gender perspectives and intersectionality across approaches

Energy education must include diverse gender perspectives, examples of women’s contributions, and analysis of inequalities (e.g., energy poverty disproportionately affecting women). SSH perspectives should be integrated to deepen understanding of governance, justice, and social dynamics. Energy education must systematically integrate intersectional analysis, recognizing that energy systems and their impacts are shaped by and reproduce inequalities across gender, class, race, geography, and other axes of difference. This requires including diverse examples of women’s contributions to energy transitions, which are often invisible in mainstream narratives dominated by male engineers and policymakers. Curricula should analyse how energy poverty disproportionately affects women and/from marginalized communities.

7. Invest in teachers as agents of the energy transition

Teachers require structured training in energy literacy, gender-sensitive pedagogy, and inclusive teaching practices. Career guidance must be modernised, start earlier, and present the wide interdisciplinary landscape of energy careers - not just technical roles.

8. Expand mentoring, sponsorship, and internship pathways

Mentorship programmes – especially those involving female professionals – help girls and gender-diverse students envision themselves in the energy sector. Internships and role-model visibility are essential to break the “male domain” perception.

9. Showcase the full diversity of careers in the energy sector

Policymakers, educators and all actors should ensure young people learn about all roles: engineering, policy, digitalisation, community energy, social innovation, modelling, data, ethics and governance. Expanding the perceived map of energy careers increases inclusiveness and meets future skills demand.

10. Ensure lifelong learning supports an inclusive energy workforce

Energy systems change rapidly. Policymakers must support continuous upskilling and reskilling, ensuring women and underrepresented groups have equal access to training, leadership programmes, and gender-aware workplace education to improve retention and career progression.

Guidebook: How to Make Energy a Core Learning Theme Across the Entire Education Pathway

1. Make Energy a Core Theme Across All Stages of Education (with Mainstreamed Gender Sensitivity)

Primary & Lower Secondary

- Introduce energy literacy through hands-on activities, simple experiments, and everyday examples.
- Use diverse role models to counter early gender stereotypes.
- Present energy as an accessible, everyday topic – not a “difficult technical subject.”

Upper Secondary

- Connect energy to real-world issues: mobility, costs, sustainability, justice.
- Treat energy as an interdisciplinary theme linking various subjects.
- Strengthen career guidance to present energy fields as inclusive and diverse.

Higher Education

- Embed gender-sensitive energy perspectives in both STEM and SSH programmes.
- Expand mentoring, sponsorship, and visibility of female role models.

- Promote interdisciplinary courses linking technology, policy, society, and the environment.

Key message:

Continuous integration of energy education – from early childhood through adulthood – is essential for building energy literacy, dismantling structural stereotypes, and enabling an inclusive, gender-responsive energy transition.

2. Build Core Energy Competencies

Energy Citizenship Skills

- Enhance basic energy literacy (systems, transitions, everyday energy practices).
- Develop critical thinking and participatory skills for engaging in public debates.
- Increase awareness of rights, community energy options, and justice dimensions.
- Foster collaboration and problem-solving in civic energy decisions.

Energy Consumer Skills (Informed Decision-Making)

- Improve understanding of bills, tariffs, efficiency measures, and household technologies.
- Teach digital skills for smart meters, apps, and home energy management systems.
- Strengthen risk assessment (e.g., comparing suppliers, contracts).
- Promote low-carbon, sustainability-oriented everyday choices.

Energy Career Skills

- Build strong STEM & SSH foundations with interdisciplinary thinking.
- Train in systems thinking, project management, and energy policy basics.
- Enhance digital and green skills relevant to emerging technologies.
- Develop leadership, communication, teamwork, and negotiation abilities.

- Ensure continuous upskilling to match rapidly changing technologies.

3. Integrate Energy Through Inclusive, Real-World Narratives

- Link energy to social practices and daily life.
- Highlight the disproportionate impact of energy poverty on women.
- Promote gender-inclusive energy solutions and policy approaches.

4. Make Women and Gender-Diverse Contributions Visible

- Incorporate examples of women's achievements in teaching materials.
- Invite female engineers, researchers, and community leaders as guest speakers.
- Use school newsletters and digital channels to highlight gender-energy stories.

5. Use Inclusive and Accessible Language

- Apply gender-inclusive language in educational and professional materials.
- Avoid implying that technical aspects of energy are “more suitable” for one gender.
- Use neutral descriptions for roles in experiments and group work.
- Explain energy concepts clearly to counteract the stereotype that energy is “too technical.”

6. Normalise Women's Professional Presence in Energy

- Present women's participation as standard, not exceptional.
- Avoid gendered metaphors or "masculine-coded" framings of technology.
- Ensure diversity in visuals and examples across learning materials.

7. Empower Teachers as Agents of Change

Teacher Training

- Provide structured training in energy literacy and gender-sensitive pedagogy.
- Address unconscious bias and promote inclusive teaching practices.
- Include examples of female experts across STEM and SSH.
- Frame energy through real-world narratives rather than narrow technical abstractions.

Career Guidance

- Modernise career guidance and introduce it earlier in the education pathway.
- Present the interdisciplinary nature of the energy transition.
- Develop clear and accessible information on energy careers.

Student Competencies

- Teach how energy systems shape social inequalities.
- Develop awareness of whose voices are included or excluded in energy debates.
- Prepare students to participate meaningfully in democratic decision-making about energy futures.

8. Strengthen Gender Diversity Across the Energy Talent Pipeline

Mentoring & Internship Programmes

- Establish long-term mentoring programmes for girls and young women.
- Provide mentors with training in inclusive communication and bias awareness.
- Develop partnerships with energy companies, research institutes, and municipalities.
- Offer paid internships with meaningful tasks: modelling, data analysis, fieldwork, community energy projects.
- Collect feedback and improve programmes annually.

Critical Thinking on Gender and Energy

- Encourage students to analyse who designs, benefits from, and influences energy systems.
- Equip them to identify and challenge structural inequalities.

Encouraging Girls and Gender-Diverse Students

- Actively promote STEM-energy pathways.
- Showcase female professionals and allies.
- Challenge stereotypes and normalise inclusive participation.

9. Diversify the Map of Energy Careers

- Present the full spectrum of careers: engineering, digitalisation, policy, modelling, social innovation, community energy.
- Emphasise that the energy transition requires many forms of expertise – not only technical skills.

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